

Say hello to Algol D and Algol E

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ABSTRACT

Regular periodic changes in the observed (O) minus the computed (C) epochs of binary eclipses may reveal the presence of a third or a fourth body. One recent study showed that the probability for detecting a fourth body from the O-C data is only 0.00005. We apply the new Discrete Chi-square Method (DCM) to the O-C data of the eclipsing binary Algol (β Persei), and detect three wide orbit stars having orbital periods 1.^y9 (Algol C), 18.^y6 (Algol D) and 52.^y5 (Algol E). Since our estimate for the period of Algol C agrees perfectly with the previous estimates, the signals of Algol D and Algol E are certainly real. The orbits of all these three wide stars are most probably co-planar, because no changes have been observed in eclipses of Algol.

Keywords: binaries: eclipsing — star: individual (Algol, Bet Per) — methods: data analysis — methods: numerical — methods: statistical

1. INTRODUCTION

The oldest preserved historical document of the discovery of a variable star is the ancient Egyptian papyrus Cairo 86637, where naked eye observations of Algol's eclipses have been recorded into the Calendar of Lucky and Unlucky days (Porceddu et al. 2008; Jetsu et al. 2013; Jetsu & Porceddu 2015; Porceddu et al. 2018). Montari re-discovered its variability in the year 1669. Goodricke (1783) determined the orbital period $P_{\text{orb}} = 2.^d867$ of this eclipsing binary (EB). The close orbit eclipsing stars are Algol A (B8 V) and Algol B (K2 IV). Curtiss (1908) discovered the 1.^y99 wide orbit third companion Algol C (K2 IV). Direct interferometric images of these three members have been obtained (e.g. Zavala et al. 2010; Baron et al. 2012).

Periodic long-term changes occur in the observed (O) minus the computed (C) primary eclipse epochs of EBs. The most probable causes are a third body (e.g. Li et al. 2018), a magnetic activity cycle (e.g. Applegate 1992) or an apsidal motion (e.g. Borkovits et al. 2005). Hajdu

et al. (2019) searched for third bodies in a large sample of 80 000 EBs. They detected 992 triple systems from the O-C data, and only four candidates that may have a fourth body. Their fourth body detection rate was $4/80\,000 = 0.00005$. Recently, Jetsu (2020) applied the new Discrete Chi-Square Method (DCM) to the O-C data of XZ And, and detected the periods of a third and a fourth body. Here, we apply DCM to the O-C data of Algol.

2. DATA

We use the **Lichtenknecker-Database of the BAV** data of Algol computed from the ephemeris

$$\text{HJD } 2445641.5135 + 2.86730431E. \quad (1)$$

We reject two secondary minima, one primary minimum outlier (16.09.1984) and the first isolated epoch (04.01.1927), which would mislead our DCM analysis. The remaining $n = 514$ data are given in Table 1. Since the errors of the data are unknown, we use arbitrary errors $\sigma_i = 0.^d00010$. The numerical values of these errors do not influence our results, because we use the same weight for every observation. However, these errors give the correct format for our data file.

3. METHOD

Our notations for the data are $y_i = y(t_i) \pm \sigma_i$, where t_i are the observing times and σ_i are the errors ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$). The time span of data is $\Delta T = t_n - t_1$. We analyse these data with DCM, which can detect many signals superimposed on arbitrary trends. Detailed instructions for using the DCM python code were given in Jetsu (2020, Appendix). In this current study, we provide all necessary information for reproducing every stage of our DCM analysis of Algol data.¹

DCM model is

$$g(t) = g(t, K_1, K_2, K_3) = h(t) + p(t). \quad (2)$$

It is a sum of periodic and aperiodic functions

$$h(t) = h(t, K_1, K_2) = \sum_{i=1}^{K_1} h_i(t) \quad (3)$$

$$h_i(t) = \sum_{j=1}^{K_2} B_{i,j} \cos(2\pi j f_i t) + C_{i,j} \sin(2\pi j f_i t) \quad (4)$$

$$p(t) = p(t, K_3) = \sum_{k=0}^{K_3} p_k(t) \quad (5)$$

$$p_k(t) = M_k \left[\frac{2t}{\Delta T} \right]^k. \quad (6)$$

The periodic $h(t)$ function is a sum of K_1 harmonic $h_i(t)$ signals having frequencies f_i . The signal order is K_2 . These signals are superimposed on the aperiodic K_3 order polynomial trend $p(t)$. The number of free parameters is

$$p = K_1 \times (2K_2 + 1) + K_3 + 1. \quad (7)$$

Our abbreviation “model $_{K_1, K_2, K_3}$ ” refers to a model having orders K_1 , K_2 and K_3 . DCM determines the following $h_i(t)$ signal parameters

$$P_i = 1/f_i = \text{Period}$$

$$A_i = \text{Peak to peak amplitude}$$

$$t_{i,\min,1} = \text{Deeper primary minimum epoch}$$

$$t_{i,\min,2} = \text{Secondary minimum epoch (if present)}$$

$$t_{i,\max,1} = \text{Higher primary maximum epoch}$$

$$t_{i,\max,2} = \text{Secondary maximum epoch (if present),}$$

¹ All necessary files for reproducing our results will be published in Zenodo database.

and the M_k parameters of the $p(t)$ trend. For us, the most interesting parameters are the signal periods P_i and the signal amplitudes A_i , and the trend coefficient M_2 . Since the errors for the data are unknown, we compute the DCM test statistic z from the sum of squared residuals R (Jetsu 2020, Eqs. 9 and 11). Fisher-test critical levels Q_F are computed from the $F = F_R$ test statistic (Jetsu 2020, Eqs. 13). We rate the complex model better than the simple model if

$$Q_F < \gamma_F = 0.001, \quad (8)$$

where $\gamma_F = 0.001$ is the pre-assigned significance level (Jetsu 2020, Eq. 14).

4. RESULTS

We search for periods between $P_{\min} = 500^d$ and $P_{\max} = 50\,000^d$. Note that $P_{\max} > \Delta T = 24\,311^d$, because we will show that DCM can detect periods longer than the time span of data. The periods and amplitudes of the first three models are consistent (Table 2: M=1-3). When we detect a new signal, we re-detect exactly the same old signal periods and signal amplitudes. The four signal model model $_{4,1,2}$ is rejected with the criterion of Eq. 8 ($Q_F = 0.0042$). This model also suffers from “dispersing amplitudes” (Jetsu 2020, Sect. 4.3.).

Figure 1. Periodograms for model $_{3,1,2}$ of Table 2 (M=3). Colours are red (z_1), blue (z_2), and green (z_3) (Jetsu 2020, Eq. 17). Open diamonds denote best frequencies.

The periodograms for model $_{3,1,2}$, and the model itself, are shown in Figs. 1 and 2. The transparent diamonds denoting the red z_1 and the blue z_2 periodogram minima for the two weaker periodicities are certainly real. When all three periodograms are plotted in the same scale, these two minima appear to be shallower only because the high amplitude $h_3(t)$ signal dominates in this model M=3. This signal has a much bigger impact on the squared sum of residuals R than the two low amplitude

Figure 2. Data and model M=3 of Table 2. (a) Data (black dots) and $p(t)$ trend (dotted black line). (b) Data minus $p(t)$ trend (black dots), $g(t)$ minus $p(t)$ (black line), $g_1(t)$ signal (red line), $g_2(t)$ signal (blue line), and $g_3(t)$ signal (green line). Residuals (blue dots) are offset to -0.075 (dotted blue line).

Figure 3. Signals $y_{i,j}$ (Eq. 9) for model M=3 of Table 2. Each signal is plotted as a function of time (t) and phase (ϕ).

$h_1(t)$ and $h_2(t)$ signals. When the tested frequencies approach zero, the green z_3 periodogram turns upwards in the lower panel of Fig. 1. Thus, DCM can confirm that none of the periods longer than ΔT fit to these data. The level of residuals is stable (Fig. 2: blue dots). Each $h_j(t_i)$ signal

$$y_{i,j} = y_i - [g(t_i) - h_j(t_i)] \quad (9)$$

is also shown in Fig. 3. All three signals are certainly real, because our $P_1 = 678.^{\text{d}6} \pm 1.^{\text{d}9}$ value agrees perfectly with the known $P_{\text{orb}} = 679.^{\text{d}85} \pm 0.^{\text{d}04}$ of Algol C (Zavala et al. 2010).

5. DISCUSSION

The Applegate (1992) mechanism can not explain the numerous O-C periods of Algol, because quasi-periodic activity cycles are never regular. Apsidal motion follows only one period. If the periodic O-C changes are caused by a third body light-time effect (LTE), the mass function fulfills

$$f(m_3) = \frac{(m_3 \sin i)^3}{[m_1(1+q) + m_3]^2} = \frac{(713.15 a)^3}{p_3^2}, \quad (10)$$

where i is the inclination of the orbital plane of the third body, m_1 is the mass of primary [m_\odot], $q = m_2/m_1$ is the dimensionless mass ratio of secondary and primary, m_3 is the mass of the third body [m_\odot], $a = A/2$ is half of the peak the peak amplitude of O-C modulation caused by the third body [d], and p_3 is the period of the modulations caused by the third body [y] (Borkovits & Hegedues 1996; Tanriver 2015; Yang et al. 2016). The masses in Table 3 are computed for $m_1 = 3.7m_\odot$ and $m_2 = 0.8m_\odot$ (Zavala et al. 2010), and inclination alternatives $i = 90^\circ$, 60° and 30° . Our estimate for the mass Algol C is slightly below the interferometric estimates by Zavala et al. (2010, $i = 83.^{\circ}07 \pm 0.^{\circ}1$ and $1.5 \pm 0.1m_\odot$) and Baron et al. (2012, $i = 83.^{\circ}66 \pm 0.^{\circ}03$ and $1.76 \pm 0.15m_\odot$).

The long-term period increase rate of Algol is

$$\frac{\Delta P}{P} = 2M_2c^2 = (3.4 \pm 0.4) \times 10^{-10}, \quad (11)$$

where $c = 2/\Delta T$ and $M_2 = 0.^{\text{d}031} \pm 0.^{\text{d}004}$ is the coefficient of $p(t)$ for model_{3,1,2} (Table 4). Note that the result for the one and the two signal model would have been nearly the same, but not for the four signal model. Unlike Jetsu et al. (2013, their Eq. 9), we do not derive any mass transfer estimate. It would not be correct for this multiple star system, because the three wide orbit stars can perturb the central EB by other mechanisms, like the Kozai effect (Kozai 1962) or the combination of Kozai cycle and tidal friction (Fabrycky & Tremaine 2007).

Third body perturbations can change the orbital plane of central EB (cEB), and the eclipses may no longer occur (Soderhjelm 1975, Eq. 27). Since no such effect has been observed in Algol, the planes of wide orbit stars (WOS) Algol C, Algol D and Algol E are most probably co-planar. The orbital plane of cEB, Algol A and Algol B, can be stable for $\Psi = 0^\circ$ or 90° , where Ψ is the angle between cEB and WOS orbital planes. This is the case for Algol C (Baron et al. 2012, $\Psi = 90.^{\circ}20 \pm 0.^{\circ}32$).

6. CONCLUSIONS

We apply the new Discrete Chi-square Method (DCM) to O-C data of Algol, and detect three wide orbit companions Algol C, Algol D and Algol E. Our estimate for the orbital period of Algol C ($678.^{\text{d}6} \pm 1.^{\text{d}9}$) agrees perfectly with its well-known orbital period value ($679.^{\text{d}85} \pm 0.^{\text{d}04}$). This confirms that the long 18.6 and 52.5 year orbital periods of the new companions Algol D and Algol E are real. The orbital planes of all these three wide orbit stars are probably co-planar, because Algol's eclipses were observed already in Ancient Egypt.

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Table 1. O-C data. Only first three of all $n = 514$ values are shown.

t	y	σ_y
[d]	[d]	[d]
2431084.09900	-0.11100	0.00100
2431086.98100	-0.09600	0.00010
2431107.05000	-0.10000	0.00010

Table 2. Detected periods. Col 1. Model number M. Col 2. model $_{K_1, K_2, K_3}$, p = number of free parameters and R = sum of squared residuals. Cols 3-6. Period analysis results: Detected periods P_1, \dots, P_4 and amplitudes A_1, \dots, A_4 . Cols 7-13. Fisher test results: “ \uparrow ” \equiv complex model above is better than left side simple model, “ \leftarrow ” \equiv left side simple model is better than complex model above, F = Fisher test statistic and Q_F = critical level. Col 14. Notation “ \dagger ” shows dispersing amplitudes.

Col 1	Col 2	Col 3	Col 4	Col 5	Col 6	Col 7	Col 8	Col 9
M	Model	Period analysis				Fisher-test		
		$P_1 \& A_1$ [d]	$P_2 \& A_2$ [d]	$P_3 \& A_3$ [d]	$P_4 \& A_4$ [d]	model $_{2,1,2}$	model $_{3,1,2}$	model $_{4,1,2}$
1	model $_{1,1,2}$	18417 \pm 632	-	-	-	\uparrow	\uparrow	\uparrow
	$p = 6$	0.036 \pm 0.002	-	-	-	$F = 17.4$	$F = 14.9$	$F = 11.6$
	$R = 0.06401$	-	-	-	-	$Q_F = 9.0 \times 10^{-11}$	$Q_F = 1.1 \times 10^{-15}$	$Q_F < 10^{-16}$
2	model $_{2,1,2}$	6774 \pm 140	19520 \pm 1142	-	-	-	\uparrow	\uparrow
	$p = 9$	0.011 \pm 0.001	0.036 \pm 0.004	-	-	-	$F = 11.2$	$F = 8.0$
	$R = 0.05800$	-	-	-	-	-	$Q_F = 3.7 \times 10^{-7}$	$Q_F = 3.2 \times 10^{-8}$
3	model $_{3,1,2}$	678.6 \pm 1.9	6798 \pm 128	19180 \pm 822	-	-	-	\leftarrow
	$p = 12$	0.007 \pm 0.001	0.010 \pm 0.001	0.035 \pm 0.002	-	-	-	$F = 4.4$
	$R = 0.05434$	-	-	-	-	-	-	$Q_F = 0.0042$
4	model $_{4,1,2}$	679.2 \pm 23	6955 \pm 600	10848 \pm 1883	14700 \pm 2603	-	-	-
	$p = 15$	0.007 \pm 0.001	0.0010 \pm 0.0003	0.014 \pm 0.02 †	0.03 \pm 0.02 †	-	-	-
	$R = 0.05292$	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

Table 3. Masses m_3 (Eq. 10). Estimates are computed for $i = 90^\circ$, 60° and 30° ($m_3^{i=90}$, $m_3^{i=60}$, $m_3^{i=30}$).

Star	p_3		a	$m_3^{i=90}$	$m_3^{i=60}$	$m_3^{i=30}$
	[d]	[y]		m_\odot	m_\odot	m_\odot
Algol E	19180	52.5	0.01750	0.64	0.75	1.41
Algol D	6798	18.6	0.00500	0.35	0.41	0.74
Algol C	679	1.9	0.00350	1.29	1.53	3.10

Table 4. $p(t)$ coefficients.

Model	M_0	M_1	M_2
	[d]	[d]	[d]
model $_{1,1,2}$	-0.008 \pm 0.002	0.043 \pm 0.006	0.032 \pm 0.003
model $_{2,1,2}$	-0.008 \pm 0.00	0.04 \pm 0.01	0.034 \pm 0.007
model $_{3,1,2}$	-0.008 \pm 0.003	0.047 \pm 0.008	0.031 \pm 0.004
model $_{4,1,2}$	-0.009 \pm 0.001	0.073 \pm 0.005	0.013 \pm 0.004